

2. Spiders collected from rice straw bundles placed in ricefields after harvest. IRRI, 1989.

also *Oxyopes* spp., *Tetragnatha* spp., *Argiope* sp., and *Dyschiriognatha* sp.

Plants and leafhoppers also were collected. It is important that several species of pests colonize the tents because they are needed as food for the beneficial species. □

M-phase in eggs of *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant)

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Growth and development of *N. virescens* from fertilized egg (zygote) to maturity depend largely on a coordinated sequence of increases in cell numbers, size, and differentiation. Somatic egg cells undergo cyclic events, such as interphase and M-phase (mitotic). The M-phase is a critical stage in embryonic development and an ideal stage for preventing rice pest development. It includes nuclear (karyokinesis) and cytoplasmic (cytokinesis) divisions. We characterized the M-phase in *N. virescens* eggs.

The insect was mass-reared on TN1 rice plants in the IRRI insectary. Eggs were collected daily from 1 to 8 d after oviposition and the onset of cleavage or nuclear division determined. (At $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, *N.*

virescens eggs normally hatch 9 d after oviposition.)

Eggs were placed on a spot-plate with 2-3 drops of Ringer's solution and squashed with a glass rod for 1 min. Extracted chorions were fixed with Carnoy's solution (3 parts ethyl alcohol, 1 part glacial acetic acid) for 20 min.

One drop was placed on a fresh glass slide and air-dried for 15 min. A drop of 60% acetic acid was added to each slide and allowed to stand another 10-20 min. One drop of lacto-acetorcein was added and the mixture squashed with a bent needle.

1. Frequency of M-phase during nuclear division in *N. virescens* eggs at different days after oviposition, IRRI, 1989. n = 1,900 eggs.

Slides were viewed under oil immersion objective (1250x) of a binocular microscope fitted with a linear micrometer.

The M-phase of cleavage was monitored in 1,900 eggs. No nuclear division was found the first 4 d, when embryogenic cells were at the prophase stage. Onset of the M-phase was on day 5; it increased on day 6. Frequency of nuclear division peaked on day 7-8. A range of 13-37 dividing nuclei was observed during peak periods. It appears 6- to 8-d-old eggs (eyespot stage to dark egg stage) are ideal for observing nuclear division stages (Fig. 1, 2). □

2. Egg cells of *N. virescens* undergoing different stages of mitosis. a = interphase, b = prophase, c = prometaphase, d = metaphase. IRRI, 1989.

Weed management

Yield loss to weeds in upland rice at Parwanipur, Nepal

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We assessed yield loss due to weeds in dry seeded upland rice at Parwanipur in 1988.

Ghaiya 2 (MW10) was seeded 18 Jun at 20-cm spacing. The experimental field was fertilized with 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha. Half the N and all the P and K were applied basal; the remaining N was topdressed in two equal splits at 25 and 55 d after seeding.

Ten 5- × 3-m plots with different levels of weed infestation were established. Two samples of weeds within a 1-m² quadrat placed randomly in each plot were taken before maturity.

Weeds were identified, dried, and weighed. Rice yield from 5.6-m² areas was converted into g/m². A simple linear regression and correlation analysis was used to assess rice yield loss due to weed infestation.

Echinochloa colona, *E. crus-galli*, *Cyperus difformis*, *C. iria*, and *C. rotundus* were dominant.

The linear relationship ($r = 0.9602^{**}$) between dry weed weight and rice yield was negative and highly significant (see figure). The regression analysis $Y = 294.579 - 1.0568^{**} (\pm 0.3638) X$ estimated the reduction in